

Luminescence Study of Trisalicylato bis (1 : 10 phenanthroline) Samarium and Trisalicylaldehydato (1 : 10 phenanthroline) Samarium

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Preparation and spectral properties of Trisalicylato bis (1 : 10 phenanthroline) Sm and Trisalicylaldehydato (1 : 10 phenanthroline) Sm are reported. It is found that on introduction of phenanthroline both the absorption and emission probabilities of $f-f$ transitions of the central metal ion are increased considerably in comparison with the simple complex. The relative emission intensity is much pronounced for Sm(phen)(salicylaldehyde)₃ compared to Sm(phen)₂(salicylate)₃. Since excitation spectra corresponds to the absorption due to salicylato or salicylaldehydato group, the role of phenanthroline in bringing about the enhancement of transition probability of central metal ion is explained as due to the creation of unsymmetric field of high magnitude on the $4f$ electrons. This is corroborated by the fact that Sm(phen)(salicylaldehyde)₃, which is more asymmetric, emits more strongly than Sm(phen)₂(salicylate)₃ which has more symmetric configuration due to the presence of two phenanthroline groups.

The study of the complexes of Sm, Eu, Tb and Dy is interesting because when these complexes are excited by near U.V. radiation, the energy absorbed in the ligand moiety is transferred to the higher energy levels of the central metal ion and characteristic line emission of the metal occurs. This transfer of energy and consequent line emission depends on the nature of bonding between the ligand and the metal ion and on the relative position of their respective energy levels. In the last few years emission behaviour of large number of R.E. complexes especially diketonates have been studied and interesting generalisation have been made^{1,2,3}. We have prepared several mixed chelates of R.E. of which the luminescence behaviour of Sm (phenanthroline)₂ (salicylate)₃ and Sm (phenanthroline) (salicylaldehyde)₃ is reported in this paper. We shall discuss mainly on the luminescence behaviour of these two complexes and the role of phenanthroline in the enhancement of the intensity of emission characteristic of the metal ion.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation : Sm(phen)₂ (salicylate)₃ have been prepared according to the method previously described⁴. It can be prepared also by another method : Sm(NO₃)₃, 6H₂O (2×10^{-4} mole) and excess of phenanthroline (6×10^{-4} mole) was dissolved together in water (20 ml) and aqueous solution of excess Na-salicylate (about 1×10^{-3} mole) added drop by drop with constant stirring. The resulting precipitate was stirred for another half an hour,

1. G. A. Crosby, R. E. Whan and R. M. Aire, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **34**, 743.
2. R. E. Whan and G. A. Crosby, *J. Mol. Spectroscopy*, 1962, **8**, 315.
3. F. Halversen, J. S. Brinen, and J. R. Leto, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, **40**, 2790.
4. K. K. Rohatgi and S. K. Sengupta, *J. Ing. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 1203.

filtered through a gooch crucible and washed repeatedly with water to remove excess of phenanthroline and Na-salicylate and dried in a desiccator at room temperature. This product was sufficiently pure as evidenced from chemical analyses. The product can be further purified by refluxing the precipitate in benzene and keeping in stoppered flask overnight; large, bright, light yellow crystals separated was filtered, washed with benzene and dried at 120° for 8 hr. and analysed. (Found : Sm-16.22; N-6.02, C-59.1, H-3.53; requires Sm-16.29, N-6.08; C-58.6, H-3.37).

Sm(phen) (salicylaldehyde)₃ : K-salicylaldehyde was prepared by dissolving salicylaldehyde (1 g) in 5 ml aq. KOH(IM), 15 ml H₂O and 5 ml ethanol. Into it was added aqueous Sm-phenanthroline-chloride (prepared by dissolving 3×10^{-3} moles of phenanthroline and 1.5×10^{-3} moles of SmCl₃ in 10 ml water) with vigorous stirring which is continued for an hour after the addition. The crystalline ppt. formed was filtered through gooch crucible and washed thoroughly with 1 : 4 ethanolic water and dried in a vacuum dessicator and analysed. (Found Sm-21.91%, N-4.00%, H-3.49%; requires Sm-21.64%, N-4.04%, C-57.14%, H-3.32%). Sm(DBM)₃ have been prepared according to the method of Whan and Crosby².

Solvents purified by distillation of the E. Merck sample. The visible absorption spectra of Sm(phen)₂ (salicylate)₃ in benzene solution was obtained in Beckman D.U. spectrophotometer and that of Sm(phen) (salicylaldehyde)₃ in Beckmann DB recording spectrophotometer. The excitation and the luminescence spectra of the complexes in benzene solution from 650 nm to 200 nm have been recorded in the recording spectrofluorimeter (Farrand Optical Co. Inc.). The luminescence intensities of the solid complexes under identical experimental conditions have been compared with the help of the light scattering photometer (Brice-phoenix Universal Light Scattering Photometer) at a particular angle and with yellow filter inserted between the photo-tube and the sample, to cut to off the scattered U.V. rays, employed for excitation of the solid complexes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table I gives the visible absorption and Table II, the excitation and emission spectral data. It is seen from Table I that the λ_{max} at 402 nm for simple Sm-salt is shifted to 405 nm in the complex and extinction maximum increases elevenfold. It is known that the absorption bands characteristic of the tripositive R.E. ions are due to the forbidden transitions within the 4f shell which are permitted by electric dipole effects of the fields imposed by the surrounding anions. The nature of the bands are thus dependent upon the electric fields imposed by the ligands upon the 4f electrons. To have adequate electric dipole effect it is necessary that the field does not have a centre of symmetry as otherwise the wave functions would retain their even-odd classification as regards reflection in the origin. The strikingly pronounced extinction at 405 nm in benzene solution of Sm(phen)₂ (salicylate)₃ as compared to Sm-acetylacetonate (Table I) indicates the imposition of the unsymmetric fields of high magnitude on the 4f electrons whereby electric dipole transition probability increases considerably. In the case of Sm(phen) (salicylaldehyde)₃ the characteristic weak band at 402 nm due to Sm⁺³ ion is completely hidden under the broad and strong band around 380 nm due

to salicylaldehydato group (Fig. 1) whereby the effect of asymmetric electric field in the enhancement of transition probability and consequent increase in the extinction of the absorption band due to Sm^{+3} cannot be established in this complex.

FIG. 1 ABSORPTION SPECTRUM IN BENZENE OF SM-PHEN-SALICYLALDEHYDE

TABLE I

Absorption Spectral Data

Name of the Compound	λ_{max}	ϵ_{max}	Solvent
$\text{Sm}(\text{phen})_2(\text{salicylate})_3$	405	34.2	Benzene
$\text{Sm}(\text{phen})(\text{salicylaldehyde})_3$	380 330	3.9×10^3 8.1×10^3	Benzene
$\text{SmCl}_3^{(a)}$	402	3.40	Water
$\text{Sm-acetylacetonate}^{(a)}$	402.4	6.38	Benzene

^(a) T. Moeller, W. F. Ulrich, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1956 2 164.

TABLE II

Emission and Excitation Spectral Data

Name of the Compound	Emission bands		Energy Separation between ${}^6\text{H}_{5/2}$ to ${}^6\text{H}_{7/2}$	Excitation Maximum
	${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} - {}^6\text{H}_{5/2}$ transition	${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} - {}^6\text{H}_{7/2}$ transition		
	cm^{-1}	cm^{-1}	cm^{-1}	nm
$\text{Sm}(\text{phen})_2(\text{salicylate})_3$	17730(564)	16720(598)	1010	335
$\text{Sm}(\text{phen})(\text{salicylaldehyde})_3$	17730(564)	16720(598)	1010	395

(Figures in the parenthesis are corresponding wavelengths in nm).

Simple $\text{Sm}(\text{salicylate})_3$ and $\text{Sm}(\text{salicylaldehyde})_3$ are negligibly fluorescent in the metal-emitting region whereas $\text{Sm}(\text{phen})_2(\text{salicylate})_3$ and particularly $\text{Sm}(\text{phen})(\text{salicylaldehyde})_3$ have considerably high orange-red metal-fluorescence. Excitation spectra (Fig. 2) shows

FIG 2 EXCITATION SPECTRA IN BENZENE SOLUTION OF
 --- SM-PHEN-SALICYLATE
 --- SM-PHEN-SALICYLALDEHYDE

FIG 3 EMISSION SPECTRA IN BENZENE SOLUTION OF
 A. SM-PHEN-SALICYLATE
 B. SM-PHEN-SALICYLALDEHYDE.

that the excitation wavelength for maximum metal-emission is at 335 nm for $\text{Sm}(\text{phen})_2(\text{salicylate})_3$ which corresponds mainly to the absorption due to salicylato group. Also the excitation wavelength maximum for $\text{Sm}(\text{phen})(\text{salicylaldehyde})_3$ is at 395 nm which corresponds to the absorption due to salicylaldehydato group. Phenanthroline have no absorption in this region and the U.V. radiation absorbed by it in the complex does not seem to transfer energy to the central ion. So it is obvious that the role of phenanthroline in increasing emission intensity is through the enhancement of the probability of electric dipole transition within the $4f$ shell by creating unsymmetric field of high magnitude on the $4f$ electrons. Although, in case of $\text{Sm}(\text{phen})(\text{salicylaldehyde})_3$ we could not establish the effect of the asymmetric field on the absorption probability, still it can be concluded that phenanthroline in this complex also increases electric dipole transition probability both in the absorption and emission processes.

The relative intensity of $\text{Sm}(\text{phen})_2(\text{salicylate})_3$, $\text{Sm}(\text{phen})(\text{salicylaldehyde})_3$ and $\text{Sm}(\text{DBM})_3$ have been compared (Table III). The emission intensity of $\text{Sm}(\text{phen})(\text{salicylaldehyde})_3$ has been found to be even greater than that of $\text{Sm}(\text{DBM})_3$ which is recognised as

TABLE III

Relative Intensity of the emission from Solid Complexes

Name of the Compound	Relative Intensity
$\text{Sm}(\text{phen})_2(\text{salicylate})_3$	33
$\text{Sm}(\text{phen})(\text{salicylaldehyde})_3$	100
$\text{Sm}(\text{DBM})_3$	87

one of the most efficient metal-emitting complexes so far prepared. Since only one phenanthroline is attached to Sm, phenanthroline creates more asymmetry in this complex than that in $\text{Sm}(\text{phen})_2(\text{salicylate})_3$ where the two phenanthroline ligands can be more symmetrically arranged. The greater asymmetry of $\text{Sm}(\text{phen})(\text{salicylaldehyde})_3$ appears to be one of the important causes of such a high intensity of metal emission in the complex.

The resonance level of Sm have been shown to be ${}^4G_{5/2}{}^{5,6}$. The path of energy transfer to the central ion is probably as follows : the energy absorbed by the salicylato or the salicylaldehydato group in the complexes is transferred by the non-radiative transitions to the excited resonance level of Sm, ${}^4G_{5/2}$, via the triplet state of the ligand and drops from ${}^4G_{5/2}$ to the ground level sextet ${}^6H_{5/2}$, ${}^6H_{7/2}$... ${}^6H_{13/2}$ and ${}^6H_{15/2}$, giving rise to characteristic emission bands of Sm. Emission at 564 nm (17730 cm^{-1}) and 598 nm (16720 cm^{-1}) (Fig. 3) corresponds to the transition from ${}^4G_{5/2}$ to ${}^6H_{5/2}$ and ${}^6H_{7/2}$ respectively and the energy separation between ${}^6H_{5/2}$ and ${}^6H_{7/2}$ is found to be 1010 cm^{-1} which agrees fairly well with the value given by Magno and Dieke⁵. Emission to ${}^6H_{9/2}$ to ${}^6H_{15/2}$ levels cannot be observed as they fall beyond 650 nm which could not be recorded in this spectrofluorometer. The energy level scheme is shown in Fig. 4.

FIG. 4

The grant of a Junior Research Fellowship to one of us (S.K.S.) by the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research is gratefully acknowledged.

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Received July 17, 1968.

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6. D. G. Wybourne, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, **36**, 2301.